

How to use water flosser for beginners

Many beginners just bought the water flosser and don't know how to install the water flosser, how to use the water flosser, and how to maintain the water flosser later.

Below Aiwejay, refer to our own water flosser product manual, to explain to everyone, the use of water flosser, and maintenance skills.

One, water flosser installation steps

The first step: align the nozzle with the card position and insert, hold the nozzle and rotate it counterclockwise by 60° , so that the nozzle is fixed in the direction of the button

Step 2: Take out the hose from the hose winder and insert one end of the hose into the handle

The third step: arbitrarily fill the water container with the suction plate method

Two, water flosser usage guide

1. Open the cover of the water tank and fill it with water whose temperature does not exceed 40°C

The water tank, and then close the water tank cover (Fig. 1). When using it for the first time, add a small amount of water to the water outlet.

2. Grasp the product body with your left hand and the water tank with your right hand. At the same time, turn it counterclockwise and pull it down to disassemble and assemble the water tank (Fig. 2).

3. Insert the nozzle into the middle hole of the host until it clicks and the installation is successful. If you replace or remove the print head, please press and hold the print head removal button, and then take out the print head (Fig. 3).

4. Lean over the sink, press the mode button, adjust the pressure to the desired position, put the nozzle in the mouth and aim it at the gums and between the teeth, and press the switch button to turn it on (Fig. 4).

5. The water jet is at a 90° angle to the gums, and the lips are slightly closed to prevent the water jet from measuring and shooting. To achieve the best results, please start from the molars (posterior teeth) and start cleaning toward the front teeth so that the jet head slides along the gum line. , And make a short stay between the teeth. Know that around the gums and between the teeth are cleaned (Fig. 5).

Three, water flosser use precautions:

1. Please read the instruction manual carefully before using the product.
2. Do not rinse the water flosser with water.
3. Make sure the water flosser is dry.

Four, water flosser cleaning and maintenance

1. The water flosser must be turned off when cleaning.
2. Regular cleaning of the water flosser can ensure a better cleaning effect.
3. For more detailed cleaning instructions, please refer to the product manual.

The above is the summary of the water flosser manufacturer Aiwejay, for beginners to use the water flosser. When you usually need to use the water flosser, you can refer to the above experience. Aiwejay, as a professional [water flosser manufacturer in China](#), accepts water flosser OEM. We have more than 10 products for you to choose from.